

Analysing the Correlation between Tongue Print, Cheiloscopy and Dactyloscopy in North Indian Population: A Cross-Sectional Study

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Abstract

Introduction: Forensic odontology is a branch of forensic sciences that uses the skill of a dentist in personal identification during mass calamities, sexual assault, child abuse etc. The tongue is a crucial organ very much encased inside the oral cavity and shielded from external environment. It is a unique structure that presents both geometric shape as well as physiological texture information that may be potentially useful in identity verification. Lip prints and fingerprints are considered to be unique to each individual.

Objective: This study is being conducted to find the prevalence of distinctive features of tongue, lip and fingerprint patterns and their correlation in males and females in the North Indian population.

Materials and Methods: Two hundred individuals have been included in the study. Tongues' impression of the dorsal surface and the lingual lateral edges in maximum relaxed protraction were made with the help of the alginate which was directly applied from the level of the oral commissures up to the lingual tip. The resultant moulds were then filled with class IV dental stone, so as to derive a positive image for identification. Lip prints were recorded using a dark colored lipstick on sticky side of the cellophane tape that was placed over the lips in resting position and then pressed uniformly. The right and left thumb impressions were recorded using an ink pad for each individual.

Results: There was a significant association of cheiloscopy with gender with higher prevalence of type I, II, III, IV pattern in females and type V pattern in males. Based on association of tongue texture with cheiloscopy there was a significant association with predominance of type II lip print in the geographical texture and predominance of type I and type II lip print pattern in the physiological texture. There was a significant association with predominance of loop and whorl print in the geographical texture and predominance of loop pattern in the physiological texture of tongue.

Conclusion: This novel study has shown correlation between tongue and cheiloscopy. Correlation has been established between tongue and dactyloscopy. They have a strong potential to be used as biometrics for personal identification in a forensic scenario.

Key words: Tongue print, cheiloscopy, dactyloscopy, lip prints and finger prints.

Introduction

Federation Dentaire Internationale defined Forensic odontology as the branch of dentistry that in the interest of justice deals with the proper handling and examination of dental evidence and with the proper evaluation and presentation of dental findings. It is substantially related with identification, based on recognition of unique features present in an individual's dental structures.^[1]

Determination of individuality or identification is one of the prime issues in forensic practice. Some of the important parameters usually noted for the purpose of identification are race, gender, age, skin texture and features, speech and voice, footprints, deformities,

hair, tattoo marks, scars, occupational marks, handwriting, garments and personal articles, gait pattern, and DNA profile. But, out of all these parameters, the ones that stand out are "Tongue prints, Lip prints and Fingerprints".^[2]

The tongue is very unique vital organ and its vitality is well inscribed in Traditional Chinese Medicine as "Tongue of life". It is known to be a mirror of the oral and general health. Every individual has a unique tongue in terms of shape and surface textures. It is the only internal organ that is easily assessable to

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inspect and is difficult to forge. It presents both geometric shape information and physiological texture information which are potentially useful in identity verification applications.^[3]

Lip print patterns are unique to an individual and are analogous to fingerprints. The wrinkles and grooves on the labial mucosa in an individual form a characteristic pattern called the lip print. The study of lip prints is known as cheiloscropy.^[1] They are normal lines and fissures in the form of wrinkles and grooves present in the zone of transition of human lip, between the inner labial mucosa and outer skin. Giving the importance of cheiloscropy in forensic identification. Ball stated that latent lip prints would be available at most crime scenes due to the presence of minor salivary glands and sebaceous glands at the vermillion borders of the lips, with the latter being principally present around the edges of the lip associated with hair follicles, sweat glands in between, and secretes oils. It is due to these occasional secretions and continual moisturising by the tongue that there are chances for the presence of the latent lip prints on items coming in contact with the lips.^[4]

These wrinkles and grooves seen on lips have been named by Tsuchihashi as "sulci laborium ruborum."^[1]

Fingerprints are characterized by alternating strips of raised frictional ridges and depressed grooves on the palmar surface of the fingertips. The ridge patterns start to develop between the fifth and sixth week of intrauterine life, are fully formed by the 21st week and are permanent for life.^[2] It has been purportedly known to be a physical characteristic of an individual that does not change over time (i.e., persistence or permanence of friction ridge pattern) and can be used as a person's "seal" or "signature" (i.e., uniqueness or individuality of ridge pattern).^[5] The first rigorous scientific study on fingerprint classification was made by Sir Francis Galton in the late 1880s.^[6]

This study is being conducted to find the prevalence of distinctive features of tongue, lip and fingerprint patterns and their correlation in males and females in the North Indian population. The rationale of introducing tongue prints, lip print and fingerprints in forensic is because of their importance as an aid in human identification.

Materials and Methods

The study sample was comprised of 200 subjects, all from North India (139 females and 61 males).

Each subject was examined for any pathology of the tongue, lips and fingers that could affect the tongue print, lip print and the fingerprint. The methods of recording tongue, lip and finger prints were explained to the participants, and the consent of all the individuals was obtained.

The examination of the tongue was carried out after its prior cleaning with sterile compresses, together with abundant rinsing of the oral cavity. Additionally, the subjects were asked not to suddenly protract their tongue up to maximum protraction, but in a relaxed position which would prevent a marked contraction of the striated lingual muscles, which would alter the characteristic aspects, as well as the shape of the tongue. The purpose of the direct examination of the tongue was to emphasize morphological features such as: shape, type, characteristics of the longitudinal medial septum and the related grooves, as well as the lingual apex type.

Figure 1: Alginate impression

Figure 2: Moulds filled with class IV dental stone

The most faithful impression intended for study models is the alginate moulded impression, which has the advantages of duplicating the most minute details and coming off the model easily; we thus performed the detailed analysis for identification purposes, by taking the impression of the dorsal surface and the lingual lateral edges, with the help of the alginate which was directly applied from the level of the oral commissures up to the lingual tip in order to avoid the regurgitation reflex. The moulds resulted as such were filled, in the dental technology laboratory, with class IV dental stone, so as to have a relevant positive image for identification.

The classification given by Stefanescu et al. has been used to assess the tongue parameters and it is as follows:^[7]

Texture	Shape	Longitudinal Grooves	Lingual Apex
Physiological	Ovoid	Superficial/ Deep	Sharp
Geographical	Ellipsoid	Rectilinear/ Twisty	Septate
Scrotal	Rectangular	Perceptible/ Imperceptible	
	Pentagonal		
	Asymmetrical		

Each individual was asked to gently clean his/her own lips by rinsing in water and the lips were allowed to dry. A dark colored lipstick was applied evenly in one stroke. The sticky side of the cellophane tape was placed over the lips in resting position and then pressed uniformly. Tape was gently removed from the lips without distorting the lip print. Cellophane tape was then stuck to the bond sheet.

Although many classifications have been proposed for lip prints, the classification by Suzuki and Tsuchihashi that is most widely used, and it is as follows:

- Type I: Clear-cut vertical grooves that run across the entire lips
- Type I': Similar to type I, but the grooves do not cover the entire lip
- Type II: Branched grooves
- Type III: Intersected grooves
- Type IV: Reticular grooves
- Type V: Grooves do not fall into any of the types I-IV and cannot be differentiated morphologically (undetermined).^[1]

For recording fingerprint, the imprint of the thumb was recorded using an ink pad on white bond sheets after cleaning and drying the hand. The thumb print was taken because a thumb print will be present almost always on the object under consideration in a forensic scenario.

Although many classifications have been proposed for fingerprints, it is the classification by Kucken and Newell that is most widely used, and it is as follows:^[8]

- Arch
- Loop
- Whorl

Results

Physiological tongue texture was the most common finding, observed in 91% of subjects. Geographical tongue was seen in 6.5% of individuals, while scrotal tongue was the least common, present in only 2.5% of participants. Ellipsoid tongue shape was the predominant type, observed in 44.5% of subjects. Rectangular tongue shape accounted for 27.5%, followed by ovoid shape in 18%. Pentagonal and asymmetrical tongue shapes were less frequently observed, constituting 5.5% and 4.5% respectively. A sharp lingual apex was identified in the majority of subjects (75.5%), whereas a septate apex was observed in 24.5% of participants. Imperceptible longitudinal grooves were more common (72.5%) than perceptible grooves (27.5%). Rectilinear grooves were predominant, seen in 92% of subjects, while twisty

grooves were observed in only 8%. Superficial grooves were highly prevalent (93.5%), whereas deep grooves were present in only 6.5% of the participants.

Branched pattern was the most common lip print pattern, observed in 28.5% of subjects. Vertical grooves constituted 23.5%, intersected grooves 22%, and reticular grooves 19.5%. Undetermined patterns were the least common, accounting for 6.5% of the study population.

Loop pattern was the predominant left fingerprint type, observed in 48% of participants. Whorl pattern was present in 42%, while arch pattern was least common, accounting for 10%. Similarly, loop pattern was the most common right fingerprint pattern, observed in 53.5% of subjects, followed by whorl pattern in 40%. Arch pattern was least frequent, seen in only 6.5% of participants.

Physiological tongue texture predominated across all lip print patterns, ranging from 87.2% to 93.2%. Ellipsoid tongue shape was the most frequently associated tongue shape across all lip print patterns. Rectangular and ovoid shapes were also commonly observed. However, the association between lingual apex and lip print was statistically insignificant ($p = 0.139$).

Physiological tongue texture was the predominant pattern across all fingerprint types. Among loop fingerprints, 87.5% exhibited physiological texture, while 94% of whorl and 95% of arch fingerprint subjects also showed physiological texture. Based on association of tongue texture with cheiloscopy there was a significant association with predominance of type II lip print in the geographical texture and predominance of type I and type II lip print pattern in the physiological texture. The association between lingual apex and tongue shape with finger-print pattern was statistically insignificant.

The association between finger print pattern (left and right side) was statistically nonsignificant with the lip print pattern.

Discussion

This study was conducted with an aim to find the prevalence of distinctive features of tongue, lip and fingerprint patterns and their correlation in males and females in the North Indian population.

Tongue has been assessed by different authors such as Zhang B et al.^[9], Abraham Johnson et al.^[3], and Sreepradha et al.^[10] by the time following various classification systems with different parameters. Pradhakshana Vijay et al.^[11] has suggested the classification that encompassed all the tongue aspects.

In this study the tongue parameters were assessed as per the classification proposed by Stefanescu C.L. et al.^[7] in the year 2014. The novelty of it is that it has incorporated every aspect of tongue involving tongue shape, tongue texture, lingual apex and longitudinal grooves and this has not been followed previously.

We found physiological tongue texture more prevalent followed by geographical and then scrotal respectively. This fact is attributed to the demographic and ethnic variation. According to Abraham Johnson et al.^[3] (2018), geographic tongue was more commonly seen than scrotal tongue which is in congruence with our study. While according to Stefansu et al.^[7] (2014), scrotal tongue were common than geographic tongue. Arnab Bhattacharyya et al.^[12] (2023) and T. Radhika et al.^[13] (2017) had been noted that scrotal tongue and geographic tongue to be characteristics of female patients when examining sexual dimorphism. Kriti Garg et al.^[14] (2020) found the U-shaped tongue, was the most common finding in males, as well as in females followed by a V-shaped tongue. Scalloped borders and multiple fissures were more

common in males as compared to females.

Arnab Bhattacharyya et al.^[12] (2023) and T. Radhika et al.^[13] (2017) and Kriti Garg et al.^[14] (2020) found that male patients had septate tips while patients with sharp ends at the lingual apex were usually females which is in congruence with our study. The literature search revealed that, Hosmath G Shivakumar et al.^[15] (2021), Hansi D. Bansal et al.^[11] (2014), Iju Shrestha et al.^[16] (2019) and Amita Negi et al.^[4] (2016) found the common type of fingerprint pattern in both males and females to be the loop pattern, followed by the whorl pattern and then the arch pattern which is in congruence with our study. Hosmath G Shivakumar et al.^[15] (2021) and Amita Negi et al.^[11] (2016) found that predominant Type I lip print was observed in the study groups which is in congruence with our study. While Yogendra Verma et al.^[17] (2015) observed that the predominant patterns were vertical and branched. More females showed the branched pattern and males revealed an equal prevalence of vertical and reticular patterns. Ashish Badiye et al.^[5] (2015) found that, Type IV (27.5%) and Type III (6.25%) to be the most and least prevalent patterns, respectively. The Type II (32%) lip-print pattern was found to be most predominant in males, while Type IV (32.5%) was found to be most commonly occurring in females. G Sathish Kumar et al.^[18] (2012) observed that lip print and Type III to be the most predominant pattern in males, followed by the Type II, Type IV, Type I and Type V patterns. In females, Type II appeared to be the most predominant pattern followed by the Type IV, Type I, Type III and Type V patterns, that are found to be in contrast.

In the present study, physiological tongue texture was found to be associated with the all types of fingerprint patterns. Ellipsoid tongue shape was strongly associated with the all types of fingerprint patterns. Sharp lingual apex was found to be associated with the all types of fingerprint patterns.

Rectilinear grooves were associated with arch type pattern while superficial grooves were associated with loop and whorl type fingerprint patterns. Arch type fingerprint pattern was found to be associated with type I and III, while loop and whorl patterns were found to be associated with type II lip print pattern. Type II lip print pattern was found to be associated with physiological and geographical tongue texture. Type I and II lip print pattern was found to be associated with sharp and septate lingual apex respectively.

No correlation between the lip prints and finger prints was noted by Hosmath G Shivakumar et al.^[15] (2021) and Amita Negi et al.^[11] (2016). However, the arch type of fingerprint was found to be associated with different lip print patterns in males and females.

Conclusion

Lip prints and finger prints develop at the same embryonic life while tongue is encased in the oral cavity and all possess unique characteristics for every individual, such that these can be used as a forensic aids in identifying individuals. The present study revealed:

- Physiological tongue texture was found to be associated with the all types of fingerprint patterns.
- Ellipsoid tongue shape was strongly associated with the all types of fingerprint patterns.
- Sharp lingual apex was found to be associated with the all types of fingerprint patterns.

- Rectilinear grooves were associated with arch type pattern while superficial grooves were associated with loop and whorl type fingerprint patterns.
- Arch type fingerprint pattern was found to be associated with type I and III, while loop and whorl patterns were found to be associated with type II lip print pattern.
- Type II lip print pattern was found to be associated with physiological and geographical tongue texture.
- Type I and II lip print pattern was found to be associated with sharp and septate lingual apex respectively.

Furthermore, the variation in distribution of tongue, lip and finger print may be linked to genetic influences which vary with respect to different populations or races. Similar studies with a larger sample size in the same population may provide further information.

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